

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Self-Anticipation and Current Difference Effect in Lattice Model under Lane-Changing Behavior

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Abstract

Objectives: To develop a two-lane “lattice hydrodynamic model” incorporating “optimal current difference” and “self-anticipation” to improve traffic flow stability and reduce congestion. **Methods:** A two-lane lattice model is introduced, incorporating both “optimal current difference and self-anticipation effect”. Linear stability analysis alongside the reductive perturbation technique for deriving mKdV equations and nonlinear calculations are utilized to evaluate the model's impact on traffic stability and congestion, with theoretical results further validated through numerical simulations under periodic boundary conditions. **Findings:** The linear stability analysis reveals that the “self-anticipation” term significantly expands the stable region in the phase diagram compared to Peng's lattice model. The derived modified Korteweg-de Vries (mKdV) equation highlights heavy traffic near the critical point, indicating areas where congestion is most severe. Nonlinear calculations further demonstrate that incorporating both anticipation time and lane-changing behavior coefficient effectively reduces congestion. This combined approach smooths out traffic flow, especially in areas near the critical point of congestion. The findings suggest that drivers' self-anticipation has a differential effect that directly mitigates vehicular congestion, as drivers are better able to adjust behavior based on traffic conditions. Additionally, numerical simulations conducted with periodic boundary conditions confirm the effectiveness of these theoretical solutions in practice, reinforcing the model's applicability to real-world traffic conditions. **Novelty:** The model integrates “self-anticipation and optimal current difference”, expanding vehicles' stability and mitigating congestion more effectively than existing models.

Keywords: Two-lane lattice model; Traffic flow; Anticipation; Current difference; Simulation

1 Introduction

Over the past few years, highway congestion has become a serious issue due to rapid population growth and increased vehicle ownership. To address these problems, numerous traffic models⁽¹⁻⁵⁾ have been proposed by examining the properties of

traffic movement. Traffic models can be broadly classified into two categories: microscopic^(6–9) and macroscopic^(10–12) traffic flow models. Microscopic models, such as cellular automaton (CA) models⁽¹³⁾ and car-following (CF) models^(3,9), etc., focus on the behavior of individual vehicles. On the other hand, macroscopic models take a broader approach by examining traffic flow at an aggregate level, using parameters like average velocity, density, and flux. Among these, lattice hydrodynamic (LH)^(14–17) models have emerged as a significant tool for studying traffic flow, incorporating various effects as outlined in Table 1.

Nagatani⁽¹⁵⁾ initially created the single-lane LH model in 1998 to explain the phase transition between free flow and traffic jams in high-density traffic waves. Congestion propagation was illustrated by deriving kink-antikink solitary solutions of the modified Korteweg-de Vries (mKdV) equation. As the number of automobiles increased, the transition from single-lane to multi-lane highways significantly reduced the load on city roads. For this, Nagatani⁽¹⁵⁾ developed a two-lane lattice hydrodynamic model based on the single-lane scenario to demonstrate how lane changes affect vehicular flow stability.

Within the framework of the LH model, drivers’ capacity to modify their speed in reaction to varying traffic circumstances by anticipating the actions of vehicles ahead is known as the anticipatory effect. This is an effective stabilization technique for vehicle movement within the network. Drivers regularly adapt their driving patterns based on current operational data, integrating it with data from previous models. Recent studies on the impact of a vehicle’s “self-anticipation” volume on vehicle stability have shown that incorporating self-anticipation density can enhance traffic flow consistency. Although significant advances have been made in traffic flow models, especially those incorporating lane-changing behavior, there remains a gap when addressing self-anticipation and the current differences in lane-changing traffic scenarios. There have been few studies examining the dynamic interaction of lane-changing and vehicle anticipation in congested environments. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of how “self-anticipation and current difference” affect traffic stability and flow efficiency in lane-changing traffic systems is still lacking. This study aims to fill this gap by developing a lattice model that integrates these factors, providing insights into their combined impact on lane-changing behavior and overall traffic stability. To demonstrate the performance of this combined approach, we use mathematical analysis and numerical simulation.

Table 1. Various derivative lattice models

Factors	References
Anticipation/predictive time	Ref. ⁽⁵⁾
Curved road/gradient road	Ref. ⁽¹⁷⁾
Jerk effect	Ref. ⁽¹⁸⁾
Throttle dynamics	Ref. ⁽¹⁹⁾
Bad weather traffic environment	Ref. ⁽²⁰⁾
Connected vehicle environment	Ref. ⁽²¹⁾
Passing behavior	Ref. ⁽²²⁾

This paper’s content is arranged as follows: In Section 2, a new lattice model is formulated by considering “self-anticipation and current difference effect” (SCDE) on two-lane traffic dynamics. In Sections 3 and 4, by applying the “small perturbation method”, we derive the “stability norm and mKdV equation” that corresponds to the lattice model. We can see the variations in the stability condition with an expectation time variable (τ) and lane-changing coefficient (γ). To validate the theoretical derivation presented above, numerical illustrations are employed in Section 5 and conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2 Methodology

2.1 Modelling

This section introduces the initial lattice model and then presents the latest model, which describes the “self-anticipation and current difference effect” (SCDE).

2.2 Original Lattice Model

Nagatani⁽¹⁵⁾ introduced the initial lattice hydrodynamic (LH) framework for a two-lane roadway by integrating lane-changing movements in multilane traffic scenarios.

Figure 1 illustrates the schematic representation of the lane-changing transportation system on a roadway with two lanes. Let $\rho_{m,i}$ and $\rho_{n,i}$ represent the flow rates of two lanes, with lane shifts occurring between lanes m and n at a specified rate

$$\gamma \left| \rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0) \right| (\rho_{m,i}(t) - \rho_{n,i+1}(t)) \quad \text{if } \rho_{n,i+1}(t) < \rho_{m,i}(t), n \neq m (n, m \in \{1, 2\}).$$

Fig 1. Diagram of the lattice traffic system

The expression for lane n can be found by discretizing the equation of continuity as

$$\partial_t \rho_{n,i} + \rho_0 (\rho_{n,i} v_{n,i} - \rho_{n,i-1} v_{n,i-1}) = \gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (\rho_{m,i+1} - 2\rho_{n,i} + \rho_{m,i-1}) \tag{1}$$

The equation for lane m is

$$\partial_t \rho_{m,i} + \rho_0 (\rho_{m,i} v_{m,i} - \rho_{m,i-1} v_{m,i-1}) = \gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (\rho_{n,i+1} - 2\rho_{m,i} + \rho_{n,i-1}) \tag{2}$$

From Equation (1) and Equation (2), we have

$$\partial_t \rho_i + \rho_0 (\rho_i v_i - \rho_{i-1} v_{i-1}) = \gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (\rho_{i+1} - 2\rho_i + \rho_{i-1}) \tag{3}$$

In this case, $\rho_i = \frac{\rho_{m,i} + \rho_{n,i}}{2}$ and $\rho_i v_i = \frac{\rho_{m,i} v_{m,i} + \rho_{n,i} v_{n,i}}{2}$. As a result, the flow equation for the two-lane lattice model was formulated as follows:

$$\partial_t (\rho_i v_i) = b [\rho_0 V(\rho_{i+1}) - \rho_i v_i] \tag{4}$$

where $V(\rho_i) = \frac{V(\rho_{m,i}) + V(\rho_{n,i})}{2}$.

2.3 Baseline Models

In Wang et al.'s analysis⁽²²⁾, the anticipated effects on traffic stability were examined using a novel single-lane lattice model that was presented by

$$\partial_t (\rho_i(t) v_i(t)) = b \rho_0 V(\rho_{i+1}(t) + \beta(\rho_{i+1}(t+\tau) - \rho_{i+1}(t))) - b \rho_i(t) v_i(t) \tag{5}$$

Here, τ is the anticipation time and $b = \frac{1}{\tau}$ indicates the driver's sensitivity, an affected coefficient of anticipated density variation is β and the predicted density fluctuation at the site $i + 1$ is $\rho_{i+1}(t + \tau) - \rho_{i+1}(t)$. For simplicity, the term $V(\rho_{i+1}(t) + \beta(\rho_{i+1}(t + \tau) - \rho_{i+1}(t)))$ simplifies to the following form:

$$V(\rho_{i+1}(t) + \beta(\rho_{i+1}(t + \tau) - \rho_{i+1}(t))) = V(\rho_{i+1}(t)) + V'(\rho_{i+1}(t)) \beta \tau \partial_t \rho_{i+1}(t) \tag{6}$$

The simplified version of Equation (5) reads as

$$\partial_t (\rho_i v_i) = b \rho_0 [V(\rho_{i+1}) + V'(\rho_{i+1}) \beta \tau \partial_t \rho_{i+1}] - b \rho_i v_i \tag{7}$$

Additionally, a lattice model with the consideration of the optimal current difference (OCD) for a two-lane traffic system. The following is the evolution equation that takes the OCD impact into account:

$$\partial_t (\rho_i(t) v_i(t)) = b [\rho_0 V(\rho_{i+1}(t)) - \rho_i v_i] + b \rho_0 \lambda (V(\rho_{i+2}(t)) - V(\rho_{i+1}(t))) \tag{8}$$

where $\rho_0 (V(\rho_{i+2}(t)) - V(\rho_{i+1}(t)))$ is the "optimal current difference" among two subsequent lattices $i + 2$ and $i + 1$ at time t and λ is the response coefficient of OCD. Both the "optimal current difference" and the "driver's anticipation" effect are important components of traffic flow discipline that help to minimize traffic congestion. In the meantime, in actual traffic situations, drivers are more likely to modify vehicles based on their own anticipation findings than on anticipation findings from the subsequent lattices.

2.4 The New Model

In traffic flow modeling, the ability of drivers to predict changes in traffic circumstances based on their own current state and the actions of other vehicles in front of them is known as the self-anticipation effect. Unlike car-following models, which only account for immediate reactions, self-anticipation integrates predictive elements where drivers adjust their speed and position preemptively to avoid abrupt changes, such as braking or congestion. This effect helps smooth traffic flow, reduce sudden decelerations, and improve overall stability, especially in dense traffic scenarios or during lane-changing maneuvers. It is an important factor in traffic models incorporating human-driven and connected autonomous vehicles. To find out how driver's self-anticipated information about vehicles affects the stability of traffic flow, a new evolution equation is created that includes the "self-anticipation current difference effect" (SCDE) is identified by

$$\partial_t(\rho_i v_i) = b\rho_0 V(\rho_{i+1}(t)) - b\rho_i v_i + b\rho_0 \lambda [V(\rho_{i+1}(t+\tau)) - V(\rho_{i+1}(t))] \tag{9}$$

The current difference at point $i + 1$ is represented as $\rho_0 (V(\rho_{i+1}(t+\tau)) - V(\rho_{i+1}(t)))$, where λ represents the predicted response coefficient of the current difference. Furthermore, as τ increases, drivers happen to give a higher priority to their driving conduct, which serves to stabilize traffic flow. It is convenient to carry out a Taylor expansion of variable $V(\rho_{i+1}(t+\tau))$ and omit its nonlinear components to simplify Equation (9) as

$$\partial_t(\rho_i(t) v_i(t)) = b[\rho_0 V(\rho_{i+1}(t)) - \rho_i(t) v_i(t)] + b\rho_0 \lambda (V'(\rho_{i+1}(t)) \tau \partial_t \rho_{i+1}(t)) \tag{10}$$

Equation (3) is combined with Equation (9) and the velocity v_i is removed to obtain the 2nd order density equation as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t^2 \rho_i + b\rho_0^2 [V(\rho_{i+1}) - V(\rho_i)] + b\rho_0^2 \lambda [V'(\rho_{i+1}) \tau \partial_t \rho_{i+1} - V'(\rho_i) \tau \partial_t \rho_i] + b\partial_t \rho_i \\ - b\gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (\rho_{i+1} - 2\rho_i + \rho_{i-1}) - \gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (\partial_t \rho_{i+1} - 2\partial_t \rho_i + \partial_t \rho_{i-1}) = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Moreover, the OV function $V(\rho)$ is identical to the one found in Nagatani's model⁽¹⁵⁾

$$V(\rho) = \frac{v_{max}}{2} \left[\tanh\left(\frac{2}{\rho_0} - \frac{\rho}{\rho_0^2} - \frac{1}{\rho_c}\right) + \tanh\left(\frac{1}{\rho_c}\right) \right] \tag{12}$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Linear Stability Analysis

This section examines the self-anticipation effect on the two-lane traffic system using the linear stability method. Assume that the starting traffic flow maintains its optimal velocity $V(\rho_0)$ and density ρ_0 at constant levels. Then, the two-lane vehicle steady-state outcome for uniform vehicular flow is provided by

$$\rho_i(t) = \rho_0, v_i = V(\rho_0) \tag{13}$$

We assume tiny fluctuations $y_i(t)$ which satisfies the relationship

$$\rho_i(t) = \rho_0 + z_i(t) \tag{14}$$

After linearizing Equation (11) and substituting Equation (14) into it, one can conclude

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t^2 z_i + b\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0) (z_{i+1} - z_i) + b\rho_0^2 \lambda \tau V'(\rho_0) (\partial_t z_{i+1} - \partial_t z_i) + b\partial_t z_i - \\ b\gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (z_{i+1} - 2z_i + z_{i-1}) - \gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (\partial_t z_{i+1} - 2\partial_t z_i + \partial_t z_{i-1}) = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

In this case, $V'(\rho_0) = dV(\rho)/d\rho|_{\rho=\rho_0}$. Assume that $z_i(t) = \exp(jki + yt)$ and by replacing the expanded terms of $z_i(t)$ in Equation (11), the shortened equation can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} y^2 + [b\rho_0^2 \lambda \tau V'(\rho_0) (e^{jk} - 1) + b - \gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (e^{jk} - 2 + e^{-jk})] z \\ + b\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0) (e^{jk} - 1) - b\gamma |\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)| (e^{jk} - 2 + e^{-jk}) = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

When we expand the parameter $y = y_1(jk) + y_2(jk)^2 + \dots$ and replace it with Equation (16), the first and second-order parameters jk remain untouched, as

$$y_1 = -\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0) \tag{17}$$

$$y_2 = \frac{1}{2b} - 2y_1^2 - b\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0) - 2b\gamma\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0) - 2by_1\lambda\tau\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0) \tag{18}$$

In the case of a negative y_2 , the distribution’s steady-state solution progressively becomes unstable. Conversely, when y_2 is positive, it stays stable. From Equation (18), we get

$$-2y_1 + b + 2b\gamma + 2by_1\lambda\tau = 0 \tag{19}$$

Consequently, the neutral stability condition can be ascertained as

$$b = -\frac{2\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)}{1 + 2\gamma - 2\lambda\tau\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)} \tag{20}$$

Thus, it is possible to get the homogenous traffic flow’s stable condition as

$$b > -\frac{2\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)}{1 + 2\gamma - 2\lambda\tau\rho_0^2 V'(\rho_0)} \tag{21}$$

Keep in mind that Peng’s model’s stable state is

$$b > -\frac{2V'(\rho_0)}{1 + 2(\lambda + \gamma)} \tag{22}$$

Fig 2. The comparative phase diagram in a parameter space (ρ, b)

Figure 2 represents the comparison between Peng’s model as well as a proposed model by fixing the values of $\gamma = 0.1$, $\tau = 0.2$ and $\lambda = 0.2$. The neutral stability curve divides the phase plot into two regions: unstable and stable regions. Also, it describes the stable zones under Peng’s lattice model and the proposed lattice model. Even with a modest parameter τ , it is evident that the stable region of our self-anticipating framework is larger than Peng’s lattice framework. We implement the lane-changing coefficient γ , anticipation time τ and anticipated response coefficient λ to the lattice model, as illustrated in Equation (21) and this successfully eliminates traffic congestion.

3.2 Higher-order stability analysis

We use the reductive perturbation approach to study the higher-order (nonlinear) analysis of Equation (11) and obtain the “mKdV equation” around the “critical point”. On a coarse-grained scale, near the critical point (ρ_c, a_c) , a parameter

ε ($0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$) characterizes the deviation from the critical point a_c . We define slow scales S (for space) and T (for time) as

$$S = \varepsilon(i + at), T = \varepsilon^3 t \tag{23}$$

$$\rho_i = \rho_c + \varepsilon Q(S, T), \quad 0 < \varepsilon \ll 1 \tag{24}$$

Using Equation (23) and Equation (24) in Equation (11) and maintaining the resultant Taylor series expansion with the fifth order of ε , the subsequent equation is obtained as

$$\varepsilon^2 r_1 \partial_S Q + \varepsilon^3 r_2 \partial_S^2 Q + \varepsilon^4 (\partial_U Q + r_3 \partial_S^3 Q + r_4 \partial_S Q^3) + \varepsilon^5 (r_5 \partial_U \partial_S Q + r_6 \partial_S^4 Q + r_7 \partial_S^2 Q^3) = 0 \tag{25}$$

where the indices r_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 7$) are

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= a + \rho_c^2 V', & r_2 &= \frac{a^2}{b} + \frac{1}{2\rho_c^2 V'} + \rho_c^2 V'(\gamma + a\lambda\tau), \\ r_4 &= \frac{1}{6\rho_c^2 V''}, & r_3 &= \frac{1}{\rho_c^2 V'} \left[\frac{a}{b\gamma} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{2a\lambda\tau} \right], \\ r_7 &= \frac{1}{12\rho_c^2 V'''} + \frac{1}{6a\lambda\tau\rho_c^2 V'}. & r_6 &= \frac{1}{\rho_c^2 V'} \left[\frac{1}{12\gamma} + \frac{1}{24} + \frac{1}{6a\lambda\tau} \right], \end{aligned}$$

Assume that $b_c = b(1 + \varepsilon^2)$. It is possible to remove the quadratic and cubic measures of ε from Equation (23). After that, the reduced equation is obtained as

$$\varepsilon^4 [\partial_U Q - h_1 \partial_S^3 Q + h_2 \partial_S Q^3] + \varepsilon^5 [h_3 \partial_S^2 Q + h_4 \partial_S^4 Q + h_5 \partial_S^2 Q^3] = 0 \tag{26}$$

where the coefficients h_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) are

$$h_1 = -r_1, h_2 = r_4, h_3 = \frac{1}{2\rho_c^2 V'(-1-2\gamma+2\lambda\tau\rho_c^2 V')}, h_4 = r_6 + r_5(h_1), h_5 = r_7 - r_5(h_2).$$

Equation (26) can be converted into a standard "mKdV equation" by using the following transformations:

$$T = \frac{1}{h_1} T', \quad Q = \sqrt{\frac{h_1}{h_2}} Q' \tag{27}$$

Therefore, one can derive the standard "mKdV equation" with the correction term $O(\varepsilon)$ as below:

$$\partial_{T'} Q' - \partial_S^3 Q' + \partial_S Q'^3 + \varepsilon \bar{M}[Q'] = 0, \tag{28}$$

where $\bar{M}[Q'] = \frac{1}{h_1} (h_3 \partial_S^2 Q' + \frac{h_1 h_5}{h_2} \partial_S^2 Q'^3 + h_4 \partial_S^4 Q')$. After neglecting the $O(\varepsilon)$ terms in Equation (25), we get a modified KdV equation whose desired "kink-antikink" solution is

$$Q'_0(S, T') = \sqrt{c} \tanh \sqrt{\frac{c}{2}} (S - cT') \tag{29}$$

In order to find out the propagation velocity, the following conditions must be satisfied

$$(Q'_0, \bar{M}[Q'_0]) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dS Q'_0 \bar{M}[Q'_0] = 0 \tag{30}$$

where $\bar{M}[Q'_0] = \bar{M}[Q']$ and the expression for the "kink-antikink solution" can be obtained with the chosen velocity

$$c = \frac{5h_2 h_3}{2h_2 h_4 - 3h_1 h_5} \tag{31}$$

$$\rho_i = \rho_c + \varepsilon \sqrt{\frac{h_1 c}{h_2}} \tanh \left[\sqrt{\frac{c}{2}} (S - ch_1 T) \right] \tag{32}$$

and the obtained solution’s amplitude is

$$B = \sqrt{\frac{h_1}{h_2} \varepsilon^2 c} \tag{33}$$

The “kink-antikink solution” provides insight into two co-existing phases: freely moving and the congested phase, which is represented in the space (ρ, b) by the expressions $\rho_i = \rho_c - B$ and $\rho_i = \rho_c + B$, accordingly. Here, continuous lines and dotted lines indicate the “neutral stability and co-existing” curves in Figure 3. It is evident from Figure 3(a) and (b) that the apex of curves (ρ_c, b_c) decreases with increasing anticipation time τ , regardless of the lane change. This suggests that for both scenarios, a higher value of τ can result in more effective relief of traffic congestion. The stable region with lane shifting ($\gamma = 0.1$) is considerably bigger than the one without lane-changing ($\gamma = 0$), as shown by a comparison of Figure 3(a) and (b). Furthermore, as Figure 3 (c) illustrates, the associated stable zone gradually grows with an increasing value of γ when $\tau = 0.4$. This phenomenon shows that implementing more lanes may be advantageous for improving traffic flow stability. In conclusion, both the lane-changing behavior and the SCDE implications contribute positively to the enhancement of traffic flow stability.

Fig 3. Phase diagram with varying values of τ and γ when $\lambda = 0.2$. (a) $\gamma = 0$ (b) $\gamma = 0.1$ (c) $\tau = 0.4$.

3.3 Numerical simulation

The impact of “driver’s self-anticipation” in two-lane vehicular flow is illustrated in this section using numerical simulations in view of both linear and nonlinear stability analysis. The following periodic boundary conditions are applied to the initial densities as

$$p_i(1) = p_i(0) = \begin{cases} p_0; i \neq \frac{M}{2}, \frac{M}{2} + 1 \\ p_0 + \eta; i = \frac{M}{2} \\ p_0 - \eta; i = \frac{M}{2} + 1 \end{cases} \tag{34}$$

Here, the number of lattices M is 200 and the initial disturbance η is 0.01. As $b = 1.5$, $\lambda = 0.2$ and $\rho_0 = \rho_c = 0.24$ re-selected as the associated parameters with the SCDE effect. Figures 4, 5, 6 and 7 show the evolution of density waves with an expectation time variable τ . The cases when there is no lane change ($\gamma = 0$) and lane change ($\gamma = 0.1$) are correlated with Figures 4, 5, 6 and 7, respectively.

Fig 4. For time $t = 10000 - 10200$ s, the spatiotemporal density shifts when, $\gamma=0$, $\lambda = 0.2$ and $b = 1.5$ for various values of τ (a) $\tau = 0.2$ (b) $\tau = 0.4$ (c) $\tau = 0.6$ (d) $\tau = 0.8$

Fig 5. The density curve for (a) $\tau = 0.2$ (b) $\tau = 0.4$ (c) $\tau = 0.6$ and (d) $\tau = 0.8$ when $\gamma = 0$

Fig 6. For time $t = 10000 - 10200s$, the spatiotemporal density shifts when, $\gamma=0.1$ $\lambda = 0.2$ and $b = 1.5$ for various values of τ (a) $\tau = 0.2$ (b) $\tau = 0.4$ (c) $\tau = 0.6$ (d) $\tau = 0.8$

Fig 7. The density curve for (a) $\tau = 0.2$ (b) $\tau = 0.4$ (c) $\tau = 0.6$ and (d) $\tau = 0.8$ when $\gamma = 0.1$

Fig 8. Phase plot of the density difference $\rho(t) - \rho(t - 1)$ against $\rho(t)$ of sub-figures shown in Figures 4 and 6

Situation 1: No Lane Switching ($\gamma = 0$)

As the stable Equation (21) is not satisfied by the given values in Figure 4(a)–(c), the additional disruption will result in kink-antikink density waves. As depicted in Figure 4(a)–(d) and Figure 5 (a)–(d) that the range (amplitude) as well as the number of “stop-and-go” density waves decreases with increasing τ ($= 0.2, 0.4, 0.6$ and 0.8) and the presence of traffic jams persists until $\tau = 0.6$ and for $\tau = 0.8$, the “stop-and-go” waves die out and vehicular flow becomes regular. In conclusion, even without the lane-changing phenomenon, the driver’s self-anticipation can effectively minimize vehicular jams.

Situation 2: Lane Switching ($\gamma = 0.1$)

The simulation results, as illustrated in Figures 4 and 5, under the scenario of lane shifts with the same anticipation time variable τ are shown in Figures 6 and 7 respectively. The relationship between density waves and the variable τ in Figure 6 is similar to that in Figure 4. Furthermore, Figure 7 density wave amplitudes are smaller than Figure 5. This pattern suggests that sensible lane changes could help in stabilizing traffic flow even more by taking into account drivers’ pre-anticipated actions.

The phase variation of the density difference $\rho(t) - \rho(t - 1)$ against $\rho(t)$ for $t = 10000 - 10200$ without and with lane changes under varied τ , respectively, is depicted in Figure 8(a) and (b). The pattern displays the characteristics of chaos in behavior. As τ increases, the dots get denser and the limit cycle’s amplitude decreases as shown in Figure 8(a). Phase states merge to a stable point when $\tau \geq 0.8$, indicating that there is no density difference and the traffic system is stable without lane changes. The fluctuation pattern of the limit cycle with lane switching in Figure 8(b) is comparable to that of the cycle without lane changing. The traffic system is easier to stabilize even if the cycles in Figure 8(b) are more erratic than those in Figure 8(a) under the same τ . It is seen that in Figure 8(b), the vehicular flow stabilizes at $\tau \geq 0.6$, however, in Figure 8 (a), the vehicular flow doesn’t stabilize until $\tau \geq 0.8$. It also confirms that switching lanes combined with the “self-anticipation current difference effect” can successfully reduce traffic congestion.

4 Conclusion

For a two-lane traffic system with “self-anticipation and current difference” effects, this study proposes a new lattice model to enhance traffic flow stability and reduce congestion. The “mKdV equation’s” result and the neutral stabilization criterion are inferred to characterize traffic congestion. Through linear and nonlinear stability analysis, the model demonstrates a significant expansion of the stable region in traffic dynamics compared to Peng’s lattice model, particularly under heavy traffic conditions near critical points of congestion. Theoretical analysis findings show that enhancing traffic flow steadiness is largely dependent on the anticipation time (τ) and the coefficient of lane-changing behaviors (γ). Simulation results demonstrate that the self-anticipation current difference effect can have a significant impact on traffic flow stabilization. The incorporation of the self-anticipation term allows drivers to adjust their behavior in response to evolving traffic conditions, leading to smoother traffic flow and reduced congestion. The derived mKdV equation further highlights key areas where congestion is likely to occur and the validation through numerical simulations confirms the model’s practical applicability under periodic boundary conditions. Further research could extend this model by exploring the interaction between self-anticipation and driver behavior in mixed-traffic environments involving autonomous and human-driven vehicles. The model could also be applied to more complex road structures, such as multi-lane highways and curved roads, to evaluate the effects of varying lane-changing

behaviors. Additionally, incorporating real-time data from connected vehicle technologies could refine the model's accuracy and applicability, providing an even more robust solution for modern traffic management systems.

Author Contribution Statement

Shubham Mehta: Execution, simulation and analysis of the problem. Vikash Siwach and Poonam Redhu investigated the underlying physics, interpreted the results and supervised the work. Poonam Redhu and Shubham Mehta wrote the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

No data is associated with this work.

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